
Isolation and Characterization of Betunilic Acid from the Stem Bark of *Zizyphus Spina-Christi*

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Abstract *Zizyphus spina-christi* belongs to the family of *Rhamnaceae*. The present work revealed the presence of a pentacyclic triterpenoid “Betunilic acid” from the ethanol stem bark of the plant material which was subjected to liquid column chromatography (LCC) and purified using PTLC to obtain ZS-P1. The structure was established by various spectroscopic studies and comparison with available data. The bioactivity of this compound was carried out using some clinical pathogens and the activity compared with a standard drug.

Keywords *Zizyphus spina-christi* (*Rhamnaceae*), stem bark, Betunilic acid, Chemical and Spectral studies.

1. Introduction

Research is often performed to purify and isolate biologically active compounds from their natural sources for characterization and identification. Purified compounds that are identified can be used for further therapeutic research on a chronic condition or illness. [1,2,3] If the target compound is known, it is very easy to compare preliminary spectroscopic data with literature data or to make direct comparison with the standard sample. However, if the target compound is unknown and very complex, a comprehensive systematic approach involving a variety of physical, chemical and spectroscopic techniques is required. Information on the chemistry of genus or the family of plant under investigation could sometimes provide additional hints regarding the possible chemical class of the unknown compound [4]. The plant *Zizyphus spina-christi* from the family *Rhamnaceae* is readily distributed in the Sahara and Sahel, from Senegal to the Sudan and Arabia [5]. Different parts of the plant are being used for various medicinal purposes among the local populace of Borno State of Nigeria. These include its use as an abortifacient by the local women and for the treatment of venereal diseases, intestinal infections and as a psychotropic agent [6]. Recently, much attention has been focused on verifying the effectiveness of *Zizyphus* against cancer. In this regard, it has been shown that *Zizyphus* extract alone or in combination with other botanical formulations reveal anticancer activities on several tumor cell lines [7,8]. In the literature, quite a number of chemical constituents have been reported from different part of the family *Zizyphus*. Ghannadi *et al.* [9] reported the presence of volatile oils from the leaves of *Z. Spina-christi* (L) wild. Weinges and Schick [10] reported the isolation of a Dodecaacetyl prodelphinidin B3 from the dried leaves of *Zizyphus spina-christi*. Lee *et al.* [7] reported the presence of cytotoxic triterpenoids from the fruit of *Z. Jujube*. Hong *et al.* [11] reported the isolation of betulinic acid a ‘pentacyclic triterpenoid’ from the fruit of *Z. Jujube*. Fernanda, *et al.* [12] reported the extraction of Betulinic Acid from *Zizyphus Joazeiro* using focused micro-wave assisted extraction. Dubey and Goel [13] reported the evaluation of a downstream technique for

extracting Betulinic acid from the bark of *Z. jujuba* while Guo *et al.* [14] reported the isolation of triterpenic acid from the fruit of *Zizyphus* species. The isolation of betulinic acid from the stem bark extract is being reported for the first time in this study.

Materials and Methods

Plant Collection and Identification:

The stem bark of *Z. Spina-christi* was cleaned, air-dried in a laboratory, for a number of days and pulverised using mortar and pestle. The coarse powder was weighed and stored at room temperature in a plastic container. 900 grams of the dried plant materials was placed in a thimble. The thimble and its contents were introduced into a soxhlet extractor connected to a condenser and extracted for eight (8) hours with 4 litres of 95% ethanol. The crude extracts obtained after drying the concentrate was defatted with petroleum ether and concentrated to dryness in vacuo at 40⁰C. The dried plant extract was weighed, labelled and stored at room temperature for further analysis.

Isolation of ZP-P1 from Ethanol fraction

35g of the ethanol extract of the stem bark of *Zizyphus spina-christi* was pre-absorbed in sufficient celite. This was packed with 150g silica gel and subjected to Liquid Column Chromatography (LCC) using an isocratic solvent of hexane: chloroform at different ratios and by collecting 20ml fractions to obtain over 120 fractions. However, only three fractions were sufficient for phyto screening and antimicrobial assay and were labelled C, D&E. D&E were microbially active, hence were combined and re-subjected to column chromatography. Based on thin layer chromatographic (TLC) analysis, the resulting portion was combined into five (5) fractions D1-D5. Fraction D5 showed a single spot after crystallization using acetone. It was obtained as an amorphous white powder which weighed 30mg.

General Experimental Conditions

The ¹H-nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were recorded in CD₃OD on Bruker AMX-500NMR spectrometers with TMS as an internal standard using UNIX operating systems at 400– 500MHz, respectively. The ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ and CD₃OD at 500MHz on a Bruker AMX-500 NMR spectrometer. The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded on a FTIR- 8400S spectrophotometer. Two dimensional NMR studies (COSY, HMBC, HSQC and NOESY) were conducted using similar instrument. Mass Spectrometry was conducted using TOF-MS, Angilent series ESI (HREST-MS) spectrometer.

Silica gel columns (60-120 mesh) was used for column chromatography (CC), pre-coated silica gel TLC (GF-254, 20 x 20 cm, 0.25 mm thick, Merck) were used to check the purity of the compound and were observed under ultraviolet (UV) light (250 and 600 nm), while 5% sulphuric acid, was used as a spraying reagent and also Iodine vapour.

Results

Spectra result for compound SB-C2 (Betunilic Acid)

The Structure of the component was determined spectroscopically using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR), 1D-NMR and 2D-NMR, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and also by comparing the obtained data with already existing literature. The results obtained are as shown in the tables and figures below.

IR (cm⁻¹): 3450, 3075, 2870, 1650, 1600, 1450, 1350, 1100

The IR spectrum of compound ZS-P1 showed prominent stretching vibrational peaks at OH str, C=O str, C=C str, C-H str (unsaturated), C-H str (saturated) and bending vibrational peaks at (CH₃, CH₂, C-C).

¹H NMR(δ) 4.7135, 4.6327, 4.5837, 1.7065, 1.0036, 0.9753, 0.9515, 0.8576, 0.7516

¹H NMR(500MHz) spectrum of compound ZS- P1 confirmed the presence of five singlet at 0.75(3H,s,H-23) 0.85(3H, s, H-24) 0.95 (3H, s, H-25) 0.97 (3H, s, H-26), 1.00 (3H, s, H-27). These represent five angular methyl groups on the lupane skeleton. Another 3H singlet downfield at δ 1.70 (3H, s, H-30) represents the vinyl methyl

group C-30. The olefinic protons (H-29) resonate at 4.6 and 4.7ppm. For protons narrow range of chemical shift often results in peak overlap which was the case for compound ZS-P1.

Figure 1: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound ZS-P1 in MeOD at 500MHz

^{13}C NMR(δ):180. 3142, 152.4123, 110.7041, 80.0180, 57.5366, 52.5593, 51.1426, 49.2678, 48.2730, 43.4524, 42.7093, 40.3719, 39.3636, 38.2161, 33.3428, 32.1504, 31.5442, 28.5216, 28.0223, 27.7039, 22.6964, 19.5653, 19.0729, 18.0996, 17.1359, 15.3508.

^{13}C NMR (500MHz) spectrum of compound ZS-P1 (Figure 2) showed 30 carbon atoms with signal at δ 180 (C-28) indicating the carbonyl atom of carboxylic group. Two signals at δ 110 (C-29) and δ 152 (C-20) were due to olefinic carbon atoms indicating that a double bond is present. Also there were signals at δ 80 (C-3) and δ 180 (C-28) showing that the hydroxyl and carbonyl groups were attached at these carbons, which were responsible for the high δ value. The signal at δ 52.5 (C-9) and δ 57.5 (C-17) were due to methine and carboxylic group attachment. While signals at δ 51 (C-18) and δ 49 (C-18) were due to another methine group and carbon double bond. With methylene attachment respectively.

In the APT/DEPT spectrum of the C-NMR (Figure 2), peaks were observed for six methyl groups (CH_3) at δ 39.5(C-23), δ 17(C-24), δ 19.5(C-25) δ 18(C-26) δ 15(C-27) and δ 28.5(C-30). Eleven methylene (CH_2) peaks at δ 40(C-1) δ 28 (C-2) δ 19(C-6) δ 36 (C-7) δ 22(C-11) δ 27(C-12) δ 31.5(C-15) δ 33(C-16) δ 32.5 (C-21) δ 38 (C-22) and δ 110(C-29). Six CH (methine) peaks at δ 80 (C-3) δ 57(C-5) δ 1152(C-9) δ 48(C-13) δ 51(C-18) and δ 49(C-19). Finally, the quarternary carbon atom peaks with signal at δ 40(C-4) δ 42(C-8) δ 38(C-10) δ 43.5(C-14) δ 57.5(C-17) δ 152(C-20) and δ 180(C-28). The high value of C-17 was due to the presence of carboxylic group attached to it at C-28 and also a cyclopentane ring. Similarly, C-20 is attached to a double bond and methyl group while C-28 is part of a carboxylic group. The chemical shifts at δ 180, δ 152 and δ 110 were characteristic peaks for betulinic type of skeleton assigned to C-28, C-20 and C-29 respectively.

Figure 2: ^{13}C NMR with APT spectrum of compound ZS-P1 in MeOD at 500MHz

²DNMR analysis of Compound ZS-P1 (Table 1) showed HSQC spectrum which reveals connectivity's between the carbon atoms in the skeleton of the molecule and between C-H as well as position of unsaturation. The heteronuclear single quantum coherence (spectra) showed that there is an interaction between proton at 3.10ppm (H-3) and that of C-3 at 80.0 ppm. There is connectivity for proton H-5 at 0.80 ppm and C-5 at 57 ppm. . Connectivity exist for H-9 at 1.25 ppm and C-9 at 52.5 ppm. While proton H-18 at 1.70 ppm was connected to C-18 at 51.0 ppm. Similarly proton H-19 at 3.4 ppm was connected to C-19 at 49 ppm with proton H-29 at 4.7 ppm connected to C-29 at 110 ppm. The δ shift at 110 ppm for C-29 and δ shift at 180 ppm and 152 ppm for C-28 and C-20 were characteristic peaks for betunilic type skeleton (Figure 3).

Table 1: HSQC Correlation spectra analysis of Compounds ZS-P1

¹³ C	C (ppm)	H(ppm)	¹³ C	C(ppm)	H (ppm)
C-1	40	0.90	C-16	33	2.5
C-2	28	1.75	C-17	57.5	
C-3	80	3.1	C-18	51	
C-4	40		C-19	49	
C-5	57	0.80	C-20	152	
C-6	19	1.45	C-21	32.5	
C-7	36	1.35	C-22	38	
C-8	42	1.80	C-23	39.5	
C-9	52.5		C-24	17	0.85
C-10	38		C-25	19.5	0.95
C-11	22	1.35	C-26	18	0.97
C-12	27	1.8	C-27	15	1.0
C-13	48		C-28	180	
C-14	43.5		C-29	110	
C-15	31.5		C-30	28.5	1.7

Figure 3: HSQC spectrum of compound ZS-P1 in MeOD at 500MHz

²DNMR (HMBC) spectrum of Compound ZS-P1 (Table 2) revealed strong long range correlations between proton H-23, H-24 and C-3 at 80 ppm. Also, interaction was observed between proton (H-30) and carbon (C-20) at 152 ppm. Proton at H-29 showed interaction with carbon at 110 ppm (C-29). Interactions between proton at H-30 and C-30 was also recorded at 28.5 ppm (Figure 4).

Table 2: HMBC (long range correlation) spectra analysis of Compounds ZS-P1

¹³ C	C (ppm)	H(ppm)
C-3	80.0	H-23, H- 24
C-20	152	H-30
C-29	110	H-29
C-30	28.5	H-30

Figure 4: HMBC spectrum of compound ZS-P1 in MeOD at 500MHz

The mass spectrum of Compound ZS-P1 showed that the molecular ion peak appeared at m/z 456 in electron impact (EI) spectrum. This represents the molecular weight of the compound which was analysed as $C_{30}H_{24}O_3$. The spectrum recorded a base peak of 189 and other fragmented ions at 207, 327 and 395 which indicated a loss of water molecule as part of the fragmentation in hydroxylupenonic skeleton.

Figure 5: Mass Spectrum of Compound ZS-P1

Discussion

In the elucidation of Compound ZS-P1, Chemical shift for ^{13}C NMR ranged between 15ppm-180 ppm while that of proton was between 1 ppm-5 ppm. The characteristic of the various carbon was deciphered in the APT spectra that is absorption signals or multiplicities for methyl carbons (primary carbon nuclei, quartet) were recorded within 15-40 ppm, methine carbons (tertiary carbons nuclei, doublet) were at 48-80 ppm and quaternary carbon (singlet) were at 37.5-57.5 (5 carbons) and then two others at 150 ppm and 180 ppm, were carbonyl (C=O) carbon. The remaining were methylene (secondary nuclei, triplet) carbons whose ranges were within 20-58 ppm including an alkenyl carbon at 110 ppm. The data from ^{13}C NMR, APT and HSQC spectrum indicated that there were seven carbons without protons, eleven (11) carbons with two (2) protons, six(6) carbons with one (1) proton and six (6) carbon with three (3) protons

Narrow range of chemical shift and peak overlap was evident in the proton NMR. However, a combination of IR signals and other spectroscopic tools alongside literature data enabled the interpretation. Forty six (46) protons were initially recorded. Two additional protons were later detected, one from an aldehydic carbon with IR signal at 1650 cm^{-1} and δ 180 in the APT spectrum and an hydroxyl function with IR signal at 3400 cm^{-1} and δ 80 which gave a total of forty eight (48) protons. An addition of three oxygens gave m/z 456 which represents the mass spectrum of compound ZS-P1. A spectral agreement was obtained on comparison with data obtained in earlier studies carried out by Peng *et al.* (1998), Sharma *et al.* (2010) and Yunusa *et al.* (2012) on betulinic acid [15-17].

Conclusion

The ^{13}C , ^1H NMR, HMQC, HMBC, APT and MS and IR for compound ZS-P1 were deciphered with multiplicities, peak integration and molecular weight in order to establish the type of hydrogen, carbon and functional group and hence the molecular formula. Thus spectral studies have confirmed that the isolated compound ZS-P1 with a molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_3$ to have hydroxylupenoic acid skeleton which conforms with 3-beta-hydroxy-lup-20-(29)-en-28-oic acid commonly known as betulinic acid.

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Reference

1. Ahmad, V.U (1994). *Atta-ur-Rahman Handbook of Natural Product Data: Pentacyclic Triterpenoids*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, 2, 1102-1104
2. Hailmichael T. (2005). *Isolation and structure elucidation of natural Products from plants* Ph.D thesis, Institute of Organic Chemistry University of Hamburg, 20-29.
3. Blinov, K.A., Carlson, D., Elyashberg, M.E. (2003). Computer assisted structure elucidation of Natural Products with limited 2D NMR Data. *Magn. Reson. Chem.* 41:27- 66.

4. Steinbeck, C. (2004). Recent Developments in Automated Structure Elucidation of Natural Products. *Nat. Prod. Rep.* 21: 512-518
5. VonMaydell, H.J. (1990). Trees and shrubs of the Sahel. Their Characteristics and Uses. Eschborn Germany, P.407
6. Abdulrahman, FI (1992). Management of psychiatric problems in Borno State, Unpublished, M.Sc dissertation, University of Maiduguri. 90-95
7. Lee, SM., Min, BS., Lee, C.G (2003) Cytotoxic triterpenoids from the fruits of *Zizyphus jujube*. *Planta medica*, 69, 1051-1054.
8. Jafarian, A., Zolfaghari, B., Shirani, K. (2014). Cytotoxicity of different extracts of arial parts of *Zizyphus spina-christi* on HeLa and MDA-MB-468 tumor cells. *Adv Biomed Res.* 3:38-45
9. Ghannadi, A., Tavakoli, N., Mehri-Ardestani, M. (2003). Volatile constituents of the leaves of *Zizyphus spina-christi* (L) willd from Bushehr, Iran. *J. Essen oil Res.* 15:191-195
10. Weinges K, Schick H (1995). Dodecaacetyl prodelphinidin B3 from the dried leaves of *Zizyphus spina-christi*. *Phytochem.* 38: 505-507.
11. Eun-Hye Hong, Jae Hyoung Song, Kyo Bin Kang, Sang Hyun Sung, Hyun-Jeong Ko, and Heejung Yang. Anti-Infl uenza Activity of Betulinic Acid from *Zizyphus jujuba* on Infl uenza A/PR/8 Virus. *Biomol Ther* (2015) 23(4), 345-349.
12. Fernanda C, and SOUSA F. Betulinic Acid Extraction from *Zizyphus Joazeiro* *Pharmacognosy Magazine*, 13(50), April-June,
13. Dubey, K. K. and Goel, N. (2013) Evaluation and optimization of downstream process parameters for extraction of betulinic acid from the bark of *Zizyphus jujuba* L. *Scientific World Journal*, 469674.
14. Guo, S., Duan, J. A., Tang, Y. P., Yang, N. Y., Qian, D. W., Su, S. L. and Shang, E. X. (2010a) Characterization of triterpenic acids in fruits of *zizyphus* species by HPLC-ELSD-MS. *J. Agr. Food Chem.* 58, 6285-6289
15. Peng, C., Boden Hansen, G., Qui, S., Fong, H.S.H, Fanworth, N.R., Young, S and Zheng C. (1998) Computer assisted structure elucidation; application of CISCO-SES to the resonance assisted structure generation of betullinic acid . *J. MR in Chem.* 36:267-278.
16. Sharma, P.P., Roy, R.K.B & Gupta, A.D. (2010); Pentacyclic triterpenoids from *Betula utilis* and *Hyptis suaveolens*. *International journal of PharmTech Research.* 2(2):1528-1532.
17. Yunusa, I., George, N.I. & Amupitan, J. (2012). Isolation of and bioactivity of pentacyclic triterpenoid (Betunilic acid) from the bark of *S. latifolius* (sm) Bruce. *Journal of Natural Science Research*, 2(4): 13-23.

